

CIVIL SOCIETY TRANSFORMATION: CHALLENGES AND PROSPECTS

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Abstract

The article is devoted to the problems of the post-communist countries of the CIS, countries of Central Asia going through a transitional period, i.e. countries undergoing the transformation of civil society, in particular, the formation of a new society on the example of the Republic of Uzbekistan. It also analyzes the strengthening of authoritarian regimes in public administration during the transition period, its negative impact on civil society, the completion of the process of formation of the class of owners that form the economic and social basis of this society, its negative consequences.

The work critically analyzes the definition of civil society given by well-known and classical scholars of the United States and Europe, distorts its views, and interprets new theoretical views that enrich the understanding of civil society, based on the problems of civil society in transition and recommendations for their solution.

The article describes the features and aspects of the process of building a civil society in post-communist countries, provides indicators for assessing the formation and development of civil society in them. At the same time, the article also contains recommendations for updating the civil society assessment indices during the transition period.

Keywords: transformation, methods of studying society, civil society, non-governmental organizations, self-government bodies, rule of law, assessment of the level of development of civil society, association, political culture, legal culture, communication, civil society development index, indicators, empirical base, consensus.

Introduction

The twentieth century went down in history as a period of building civil society in Europe, North America and some Asian countries. Western experience in this area has created opportunities for ensuring human rights and freedoms, improving the well-being of people, and increasing the gross domestic product of each country. Of course, the interest of most countries in the world in the experience has grown. The goal of building a civil society has become a strategic challenge, especially for countries undergoing a period of transformation.

The collapse of the USSR in the last period of the twentieth century, as a result of which the union republics became national independent states, and democratic changes in the former socialist states of Eastern Europe increased the importance of civil society. The political elites of these countries have chosen the path of building a civil society. In particular, along with all the countries of the CIS and Eastern Europe, the state of Uzbekistan in 1991 proclaimed the creation of a civil society as a key strategic goal.

However, the past period - 1991-2015 - for almost a quarter of a century in Uzbekistan, civil society institutions have not developed, the problems in the field of human rights and freedoms have not been resolved. The election of Sh.M. Mirziyoyev as President has allowed for significant changes in this area: dialogue between the government and the citizen, deep reform of the judiciary to ensure human rights and freedoms, administrative reforms in the executive branch, freedom of the press and speech. Nevertheless, the country has not yet achieved the formation of civil society institutions that are typical of Western countries and represent human interests and rights in the political system and society.

Therefore, the study of problems in this area, finding solutions to them has become one of the most pressing tasks of the political and social sciences. During the first 25 years of Uzbekistan's independence, the government has carried out reforms to build civil society and adopted certain laws in this area, but these reforms have not yielded results. On the contrary, the fact that the state has become more authoritarian from year to year, the failure to ensure human rights and freedoms, confirms the relevance of the topic, the expediency of scientific research of problems in this area.

Materials and methods

When writing the article, the evolutionary processes of the formation of civil society in foreign countries and Uzbekistan were studied, which were brought together into a single system. The analyzes and recommendations of renowned experts on this topic were studied. The object of the article's research is the transformation of civil society in Uzbekistan. The article used general scientific research methods - comparative, logical and statistical analysis, in addition, they turned to methods of analysis of structure and dynamics, generalization, comparison and systematization of data and sources.

Literature review

In analyzing the topic, the book "Civil Society and Political Theory" was studied, in collaboration with famous American political scientists J.L.Cohen, E.Arato, containing new theories of civil society, and was used to enrich the perception of civil society. When analyzing the practical and theoretical aspects of civil society in the CIS countries, research was used by I.A.Kharichev, M.V.Evtushenko, N.Baranov, Yu.N.Vyryazhkina, I.V.Mersiyanova, K.D.Danishevsky, V.V.Elizarov, N.L.Khananashvili.

The works of local scientists, such as A.Shovkatov, A.Akramov, D.Kurbanov, M.Sharifkhodjaev, A.R.Rakhmanov, I.Ergashev, A.Kholbekov, M.Djakbarov, N.Umarova who studied the problems of civil society in Central Asia, in particular in Uzbekistan. In their research, the connection of the formation of civil society to

the activities of one person - the head of state, the interpretation of civil society as a human unit belonging to the state was critically studied.

The article also uses materials from three scientific articles published by one of the authors - M. Kyrgyzbaev in foreign scientific journals.

The main part

On the world map, as a result of the collapse and disappearance of the USSR in the early 1990s, a number of independent states were formed on its territory. Now they are called “CIS countries”. Among them, the country in the center of Central Asia - the Republic of Uzbekistan - is undergoing a period of transformation aimed at building a civil society over the 30 years of its independence.

European classical political philosophers Thomas Gobbs, John Locke, Jean-Jacques Russo, Charles Montesquieu, Immanuel Kant, Georg Wilhelm Gegel, John Stewart Mill and twentieth century scholars have clarified all the foundations of civil society. However, as this society develops, other aspects of it are also being explored.

The state and level of development of civil society in the twentieth century was studied by the famous American political scientists J.L.Cohen and E.Arato. They emphasized the legal aspects of civil society and emphasize the following. “When civil society (as it was very recently in the countries of Eastern Europe) is only being formed under the influence of social movements and other civil initiatives, it is possible that for some time it should do without the established structure of rights. Nevertheless, we intend to prove that the measure of the success of these movements in the institutionalization of civil society is the legalization of rights, and not only on paper, but also in real life. Focusing on the institutional spheres of civil society, we can distinguish three sets of rights: rights related to the reproduction of culture (freedom of thought, press, speech and communication); rights guaranteeing social inclusion (freedom of association and assembly); rights protecting socialization (protection of private, intimate life and personal integrity). Two other sets of rights mediate between civil society and the market economy (property rights, contracting

rights, labor rights) and between civil society and a modern bureaucratic state (political rights of citizens and the rights of people living on benefits). The internal relationship between these sets of rights determines the type of institutionalized civil society [4].

J.L.Cohen and E.Arato prioritized such factors as institutionalization, legal relations, social integration, socialization as the basis of civil society. These are factors that are absent or do not work in transition countries.

The economic basis of civil society is a multi-structured market economy based on private property. In modern conditions, various forms of property, being in equal conditions, competing with each other, create the economic foundation of a civil society. Non-state enterprises, cooperatives, rental collectives, joint stock companies, associations of cooperatives and other voluntary associations of citizens in the field of economic activity are the basis of the economic sphere of civil society, which guarantees the economic rights of citizens.

The social basis of civil society is the so-called "middle stratum", which in democratic countries constitutes up to 60% of the population. The middle stratum includes scientific and technical workers, managers, middle-level administrators, intellectuals, farmers, small owners, highly qualified workers, and service workers. The main features of the middle stratum are income, lifestyle, and social prestige [12].

At the same time, market relations - the basis of the modern economy - are impossible without pluralism of forms of ownership and a wide class of private owners. It is market relations that constitute the economic basis of civil society, stimulating the development of initiative and entrepreneurship of citizens. Only an economically wealthy individual is able to fully realize and exercise his rights and freedoms, to act within the framework of civil society associations in defense of his rights and freedoms, to influence public policy, consciously participating in political life, the activities of political parties, elections and referendums.

In the economic sphere, there is a wide network of civil society organizations formed by individuals and non-state enterprises (industrial, commercial, financial, etc.), which constitute an absolute majority in modern democracies. It should be emphasized that civil society is made up of associations and associations that are both commercial and non-commercial in nature [3].

One of the major problems of the transition period is the fact that the political and legal culture of the population in Uzbekistan is not completely free of previous traditions, human rights and freedoms and democratic values are reflected in the worldview of citizens due to economic and political factors.

In addition, the economic and social basis of civil society - the stratum of property owners - has not yet completed the process of organizing into a certain class. They are far behind the level of developed countries, their development is slow (see Table 1).

Table 1

World Small Business Indicators. Country statistics [15]

Business statistics in the world make it possible to compile a rating of countries in which the most favorable conditions for entrepreneurship have been created. The data are presented in the table:

The country	General rating	Place in the world			
		By the number of registered enterprises	On lending	International trade	By the number of liquidated enterprises
New Zealand	1	1	1	55	34
Singapore	2	6	20	41	29
Denmark	3	24	32	1	8

Hong Kong	4	3	20	42	28
South Korea	5	11	44	32	4
Norway	6	21	75	22	6
Great Britain	7	16	20	28	13
USA	8	51	2	35	5
Sweden	9	15	75	18	19
Macedonia	10	4	16	27	32
Estonia	12	14	32	17	42
Latvia	14	22	7	25	44
Georgia	16	8	7	54	106
Germany	17	114	32	38	3
Lithuania	21	29	32	19	66
Canada	22	2	7	46	15
Kazakhstan	35	45	75	119	37
Belarus	37	31	101	30	69
Armenia	38	9	20	48	78
Russia	40	26	44	140	51
Azerbaijan	65	5	118	83	86
Kyrgyzstan	75	30	32	79	130
Ukraine	80	20	20	115	150
Uzbekistan	87	25	44	165	77
Tajikistan	128	85	118	144	144

As can be seen from Table 1, the society and government policies of the top ten countries, which include New Zealand, Singapore, Denmark, Hong Kong, South Korea, Norway, the United Kingdom, the United States, Sweden and Macedonia, mean that all conditions have been created for the development and efficiency of small business. If you look at it from a different point of view, it can be assessed as

a result of the positive influence of a developed civil society on the development of small business in these countries.

Table 1 shows that the overall rating of small businesses in the Republic of Uzbekistan, the number of registered enterprises and their lending rates have increased significantly over the past three years. However, the problems with their participation in international trade and the number of liquidated enterprises did not decrease. Low participation in international trade means that small businesses continue to lag behind in the production of quality goods at the level of export demand. The fact that the country is one of the lowest in terms of the number of liquidated enterprises shows that the survival rate of small businesses is low, and the conditions for their development are still insufficient. This is the weakness of the factors influencing the socio-economic status of civil society. Since the well-being of society, the social development of citizens is also involved in determining the level of development of civil society.

The experience of the development of civil society in developed countries shows that the formation of the property class plays an important role in the formation of civil society. Therefore, in Uzbekistan, a number of problems have arisen associated with the transition period of the formation of the property class. At the same time, it became clear that the economic basis of civil society, the fact that the middle social class, which is the main economic and political force in the transition to civil society, has not yet been formed, does not allow the development of civil society. The sluggishness of the social and political activity of the social strata of society led to the inability of political parties to act on the basis of democratic principles. These conditions in society now began to require that the path of development of civil society in each country was different and according to different criteria. The countries of Central Asia, including Uzbekistan, also show the experience of building industrial societies in North America and Europe before building a civil society, a high level of industry and technology, as well as private property, which is becoming the basis of the economy.

According to local experts, the following are still considered the main problems in the field of small business and private entrepreneurship:

- lack of own and borrowed funds, as a result of which small businesses are unable to purchase modern and high-tech equipment;
- problems and difficulties in obtaining land plots for the implementation of entrepreneurial activities, as well as in connection to engineering and communication networks;
- lack of liquid security or this security is insufficient for a bank loan at the start of its activities, which reduces the possibility of obtaining a loan;
- difficulties in obtaining long-term loans, stimulating the formation and development of small innovative industrial production;
- ineffective mechanisms for promoting small business products to regional and world markets, as well as the complexity of competition in the external market in certain sectors of the economy and the problem of entering foreign markets;
- insufficient development of information systems, marketing, management and logistics services; insurance companies, audit firms, trading houses, consulting centers, business centers, business incubators;
- insufficient development of sales markets, as well as markets for raw materials and materials;
- poor preparation of the professional and qualification level of those employed in small business;
- a large number of regulatory authorities [11].

It is necessary to deeply study the experience of the United States, Japan and the European Union in the development of small business in the country. The active growth of the share of small enterprises in the structure of the economy of Western countries began to occur in the mid-70s and early 90s. Today, in the most developed countries of the West, small firms account for 70-90% of the total number of enterprises.

For comparison, we can take, for example, the USA - where 53% of the total population is employed in small business, Japan - with its 71.7% and the EU countries, where about half of the working population works in similar enterprises. These figures alone speak of the enormous importance of small businesses for the economies of these countries. The efficiency of these firms is evidenced by the fact that for \$ 1 of costs they introduce 17 times more innovations and developments than large enterprises, which give life to only 10% of new technologies, the remaining 90% are introduced by small enterprises and independent inventors. The development of small businesses is necessary only because they give life to old large-scale enterprises and, in alliance with them, receive significant benefits both for themselves and for the market economy as a whole. This is evidenced by the following figures: in the United States, small businesses account for 34.9% of net income, and in Japan, 56.6% of all products in the manufacturing industry are produced by small businesses [5].

One of the biggest problems in the formation of civil society in Uzbekistan is that mistakes are made not only in the worldview of citizens, but also in their imagination and theoretical analysis. At the same time, the perception of civil society in Central Asian countries, especially in Uzbekistan, is still in its infancy. In addition, in the last 30 years of independence, theoretical views on what a civil society is have not been perfected. In the eyes of most social scientists, “civil society” is interpreted as a state-run or state-owned human unit.

Including prof., M.Sharifkhodjaev wrote about the first President of Uzbekistan I.A.Karimov: He “with enviable persistence and conviction implements the ideas of civil society. It will not be an exaggeration if we say that he is the author of the concept of the formation of civil society in our republic” [10]. “Based on what has been achieved in the ongoing reforms, Islam Karimov theoretically deepens his political doctrine. Determining the main priorities for further deepening reforms in Uzbekistan at the beginning of the 21st century, the head of state in his political theory puts forward completely different ideas based on loyalty, rationality and

reality for the future. The essence of our development strategy, days of reforms and transformations in society on the eve of and in the first years of the XXI century, were defined by I.A.Karimov in his idea of liberalism" [10].

Obviously, the author connects the concept of civil society and its concept with one person - the activity of the President, which is formed by the head of state, and not citizens, and there is no difference between civil society and the state. Worshiping the dead is a legacy of the former Soviet era. In addition, the author promotes the myth of the liberal ideas of the former president, known throughout the world for the establishment of an authoritarian regime in the country.

Professor A.R.Rakhmanov also connected the construction of civil society in Uzbekistan not with citizens or non-governmental organizations, but with the activities of former President I.A. Karimov: "The President of the Republic of Uzbekistan I.A.Karimov has identified the development of spirituality, along with the economy, a priority direction of building a democratic rule of law and the formation of civil society" [8]. He goes on to write: "Fate has entrusted Islam Karimov with the historical role of a society reformer, called upon to solve the pressing problems of the socio-economic, political, state-legal and spiritual development of our state in the difficult conditions of the transition period. ... The President of the country clearly outlined our main goal: building the rule of law and the formation of civil society" [8]. Obviously, the author is trying to interpret the prospects and development of civil society in Uzbekistan without the participation of citizens and non-governmental organizations, as in a former socialist totalitarian society, linking the reforms of building a civil society in Uzbekistan with only one person - the president. The fact that his textbook does not provide an analysis of only public administration and political processes considers civil society as a human unit within the framework of public administration.

Published in 2005 in a brochure by a political scientist and sociologist professor I.Ergashev, A.Kholbekov, M.Jakbarov, N.Umarova also says that "President Islam Karimov has developed a concept for the formation of civil society in the country

and is leading its implementation"[13]. At the same time, they express their views on building a civil society only on the basis of the development of a national idea and do not express an opinion that this society should become universal.

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The following professor N.Baranov's opinion assesses the situation in the CIS and post-communist state - Uzbekistan as follows: "In the post-communist world, especially in Russia, it is perfectly obvious that the state does not seek such support and does not provide civil society with the necessary resources. Moreover, due to the political "undercover struggle" within the corrupt elite, in almost all power structures, the problems of civil society are pushed into the background by the current interests of the political class, which dominate both the media and the centers of public policy" [1].

In the CIS, Central Asia, especially in Uzbekistan, there have been no significant changes in the formation of civil society in the last decade. The participation of the population in social and political processes in society is not noticeable, the primary organizations of most political parties are not formalized, NGOs are not independent of the executive branch, the activity of self-governing bodies and participation in public life is not noticeable.

Well-known Russian scientist J.N.Vipryajkina made an in-depth study of the formation of civil society in the CIS and Central Asia and came to the following conclusions: "The monolithic civil society prevailing in Central Asia, Belarus, Kazakhstan is distinguished by a high level of social integration, adaptability, a certain kind of conformism, non-politicization, and a high degree of controllability in relations with state authorities.

The implementation of political transformation was a tough imperative for all post-communist countries. A special role in this process was played by the post-Soviet elite, whose mental and behavioral attitudes had a negative impact on the

nature of the new political and civil institutions in the communitarian-monolithic models of civil society (Kazakhstan, the republics of Central Asia and Zakavka).

Semi-authoritarian forms of state-civil society relations have also developed in Kyrgyzstan, Turkmenistan, and Tajikistan. In most of these countries, despite all the multiparty elections of the 1990s, it was not possible to create functioning parliaments or other institutions capable of effectively controlling the executive branch.

Over the years of reforms in these post-Soviet states, a mass stratum of small and medium-sized businesses was never created, and this despite the fact that the authors of the reforms considered this task as a priority, the need for its early solution justified the acceleration of the pace of privatization and often dubious methods in its conduct.

The specificity of civil society in these post-Soviet states lies in the fact that its formation takes place in the context of ongoing political transformation. Since the political and economic elites do not express a particular readiness to stimulate the formation of civil society, and the middle class cannot do this due to its small size, the main burden in this regard falls on the shoulders of the "base" and "lower", the most numerous social strata.

Of course, civil society in these post-Soviet states is still only at the beginning of a long and probably difficult path. It is unlikely that he will be able to overcome his transitional character in a short time” [2].

It is obvious that the formation of civil society in Uzbekistan, as well as in the CIS, Eastern Europe, Latin America, Africa and some Asian countries, is proceeding very slowly. The main reason for this was that in 1991-2016 there was an authoritarian rule in the country, the national security organs were strictly controlled not only by state institutions, but also by the executive branch.

In general, in 1991-2016, there was no possibility of forming a civil society in Uzbekistan. The results of reforms based on the principle of the state - the main reformer of the former president I.A.Karimov, led to an excessive strengthening of

the executive power, the emergence of the experience of the national security agencies in controlling citizens. The leadership of political parties and NGOs consisted of the executive branch, local party organizations and NGOs elected and recommended by the governors.

Since the state authorities and state institutions did not conduct civil society work among the population, they did not form such a society-specific perception. The population understood civil society as a human unit, united by the state, ruled by the state. On November 12, 2010, "The Concept of Further Deepening Democratic Reforms and Development of Civil Society" was adopted, put forward by former President I.A. Karimov at a joint meeting of the Legislative Chamber and the Senate of the Oliy Majlis of the Republic of Uzbekistan. This concept has been promoted and promoted among the population for almost ten years. However, this concept was not directly related to the formation of civil society, but was aimed at developing legislation related to this society. Therefore, even after the adoption of these laws by the parliament, reforms to build a civil society did not advance. The leadership of political parties, NGOs, self-government bodies and the media did not escape the control of the executive branch. In almost all books on civil society, the building of this society began to be extolled as a "service" of the head of state. The praise is increasing.

The problems of building a civil society in the country did not solve the problem of changing a person's worldview, not only in the sphere of society. Citizens could not fully enjoy their rights and freedoms enshrined in the law. At the same time, the underdevelopment of civil society created a number of problems for economic freedom and hindered the growth of economic potential. Expanding opportunities for the development of the middle class, which is the socio-economic basis of civil society, also remains an urgent task.

The need to further deepen the reforms of building a civil society in the Republic of Uzbekistan, which marked the beginning of the path of rapid development in Central Asia, which began in 2017, puts on the agenda a broader

study of foreign experience. The main problems of building a civil society in Central Asia, in particular in Uzbekistan, are:

in these countries, the process of abandoning national traditions in the management of society and the state is still slow;

in proportion to the socio-economic situation in society, social strata are passive in providing financial support to non-governmental non-profit organizations (NGOs) in which they participate;

since the country is in transition, the population has not yet fully mastered the experience of meeting their interests through NGOs;

demographic processes in the country are gaining momentum. This process hinders the development of the economic and financial potential of the state. For example, in Uzbekistan, the population is growing by 1.4-1.5% annually, while the GDP is growing by 5-6%;

the legal and political culture of citizens, embedded in democratic principles, has now begun its stage of development [6].

At present, the number of NGOs in Uzbekistan has increased from 200 in 1991 to 9,800 in 2020. The country used to be ruled by a one-party system, but now there are five political parties in the country. Trade unions in 16 main sectors are trying to meet the social interests of citizens. There are about 10,000 self-government bodies and 1,500 media outlets (most of them private and independent). However, the existing NGOs are small in size and have not yet fully fulfilled their functions [7].

The development of civil society in Uzbekistan has been significant since 2017. At the end of 2016, with the election of Sh.M. Mirziyoyev, the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, there have been changes in the construction of civil society, which lasted for several decades. Initially, an obstacle to the development of civil society was the importance of reforming the executive power system in accordance with the requirements of the rule of law. After all, civil society can only develop in a state that operates on the basis of democratic principles.

Initially, he carried out reforms aimed at transforming the system of state executive power, which was the main obstacle to building civil society not only as a governing body, but also as a body providing public services to citizens. Reforms in this area are based on the principle that "government agencies should serve our people, not people". 2017 has been declared "The Year of Dialogue with the People and Human Interests". On December 28, 2016, the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On measures to radically improve the system for considering appeals of individuals and legal entities" was issued. In accordance with it, the People's Reception of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan and virtual receptions of the President of the Republic of Karakalpakstan, regions and the city of Tashkent, as well as in each district and city (except for cities of subordination to the district). As a result of the work of foster citizens, citizens faced bureaucratic obstacles in various areas, the abolition of many illegal departmental instructions, the allocation of optimal bank loans, the elimination of illegal inspections of enterprises, and radical changes in law enforcement. Over the past year, public receptions received more than 1.5 million applications.

It began on September 8, 2017 with the adoption of the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Approval of the Concept of Administrative Reform in the Republic of Uzbekistan". The Concept of Administrative Reforms in the Republic of Uzbekistan combines the legal framework and the strategic concept of modernizing the executive branch in the country. Of course, the transformation of the executive power system into a governing body based on the interests and needs of the people - this began to mean the formation of traits and characteristics inherent in civil society and the rule of law in the country. This resolution approved the "Concept of Administrative Reform in the Republic of Uzbekistan". The decree describes in detail not only the tasks of administrative reforms, but also the complexities of the old management methods that impeded the development of these reforms, as well as how and under what conditions they prevent the modernization of public administration.

The essence of the concept and the tasks set in it are intertwined with national traditions and experience of modernizing the public administration system in developed countries. In accordance with this concept, on December 12, 2017, the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On measures to radically reform the national system of public services" was adopted. It is known that in a short period of time the country has taken comprehensive measures to improve the quality of public services, to create favorable conditions and convenience for business for the provision of public services on the principle of a "single window". In particular, the transfer from February 1, 2017 of the unified centers of public services to enterprises from the regional and city khokimiyats under the jurisdiction of the Ministry of Justice of the Republic of Uzbekistan is an important step in the development of this sector. As a result, the number of public services provided by these centers increased to 100.

The decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated April 11, 2018 "On additional measures to accelerate the development of public services" marked the beginning of a new stage in the modernization of the executive branch and its local structures. In the decree, first of all, the tasks of the reform on adaptation of the executive power and its local structures to the provision of public services to the population were announced. It provides for the formation of a kind of "people's monitoring", which will promptly provide information on the activities of civil servants, appeals to public service bodies, reports of their abuse of power. As a result, not only public control over the activities of the executive branch was exercised, but also civil control.

On the world map, as a result of the collapse and disappearance of the USSR in the early 1990s, a number of independent states were formed on its territory. Now they are called "CIS countries". Among them, the country in the center of Central Asia - the Republic of Uzbekistan - is undergoing a period of transformation aimed at building a civil society over the 30 years of its independence.

The experience of the past has shown that civil society, like the countries of the new and old worlds of Europe, must go through the stages of building a civil society, which will be a much more difficult and difficult transition period. In particular, it should be noted that the history of the Central Asian region did not go through the experience of a market economy and capitalist relations, the absence of a single national market economy in each of the countries of the region hinders the rapid development of civil society reform. In addition, insufficient awareness of “civic engagement” or initiatives of non-governmental organizations (NGOs) as a result of the fact that the national mentality, culture, spirituality, and spirit of the nation are not yet ready to accept democratic values, also has a negative impact on the reforms in the transition period.

At the same time, it became clear that the economic basis of civil society, the factor of the immaturity of the middle class, which is the main economic and political force in the transition to civil society, does not allow the development of civil society. The sluggishness of the social and political activity of the social strata of society led to the inability of political parties to act on the basis of democratic principles. These conditions in society now began to require that the path of development of civil society in each country was different and according to different criteria. Central Asian societies also show such experiences as the creation of industrial societies in North America and Europe before civil society, a high level of industry and technology, and the transformation of private property into the basis of the economy.

One of the main problems of the transition period is that the political and legal culture of the population is not completely free from previous traditions, human rights and freedoms and democratic values are reflected in the worldview of citizens due to economic and political factors.

Currently, the number of NGOs in Uzbekistan has increased from 200 in 1991 to 9,200 in 2018. If earlier there was a one-party system in the country, now there are four political parties in the country. Trade unions in 16 main sectors are trying

to meet the social interests of citizens. There are about 10,000 self-government bodies and 1,500 media outlets (most of them private and independent).

However, civil society building reforms have faced various challenges. They consisted mainly of:

- the social basis for building a civil society - the fact that the class of owners has not yet been formed;
- commitment of young governments to authoritarian rule;
- lack of political and legal culture of the population based on democratic principles;
- excessive share of the poor among the population of the country;
- lack of perception of civil society among citizens, their lack of experience in participating in non-governmental organizations and pursuing their own interests;
- lack of active participation of the majority of the population in the activities of non-governmental organizations and political parties.

One of the goals of administrative reforms in Uzbekistan is the formation of a civil society based on decentralization. Civil society can develop only in the case of not only horizontal, but also vertical separation of powers, that is, the balance of elected government bodies.

In the current period of reforms in the country, a new urgent task of obtaining theoretical views and practical understanding of civil society is on the agenda. In particular, indicators such as stages of development, signs, factors, the level of development of civil society play an important role in determining the prospects of countries in transition, setting new tasks, comparing their level of development with other countries of the world. From this point of view, to have knowledge of the development indices of civil society in the present is to understand one's own period.

One of the important aspects of the study of civil society is measuring the stages and levels of its development. For this in modern social and human sciences, many different indicators and indices are used. They consist of indices that classify the

level of civil society in countries or individual regions, as well as indicators of their democratization.

An indicator is a piece of information (about a complex system) that allows you to think about the state of an entire system. The growth or change of any indicator requires interpretation and understanding. In addition, at a glance, it is natural that the need for indicators to assess the situation is high.

The indices allow to assess various aspects of civil society: quality of life, self-esteem, level of freedom, level of political influence, measure of civic confidence in key political institutions, activity of the social sector, level of political and civic participation, etc.

The ambiguity and non-standard nature of many of the results obtained does not allow making broad generalizations and promising conclusions on their basis; but at the same time, the results obtained can reveal social and political changes, which will allow comparative analysis of a specific country or region.

Often the empirical basis for calculating indices consists of data collected from the population through periodic surveys on representative collection and selection (taking into account gender, age, education and contribution or share in regional zoning). We are thinking about some indicators and indicators of the development of civil society and the levels of its democratization, which are more important in this regard.

CIVICUS Civil Society Index. Since 2005, in some CIS countries, the CIVICUS Civil Society Index is based on a project of the World Union of Civil Participation. The project focused on researching civil society organizations and promoting civic engagement. The index reflects the state of civil society structures, the external environment in which they live and work, the values that civil society organizations adhere to and protect, as well as the influence of these organizations.

The measurement of these structures includes the activity of the non-state social sector in the country and its measurement, its components, interaction procedures, resources belonging to civil society institutions. The measurement of the external

environment is based on the following dimensions: values, norms and attitudes promoted and expressed by civil society institutions, consensus and disagreements between them.

Measurement of values concerns the legal, political and socio-cultural conditions for the functioning and development of civil society, its interaction with government, business and international non-governmental organizations. Impact measurement is concerned with assessing the net impact of civil society in finding solutions to socio-economic and political problems. Separate indicators have been developed for each of these parameters. Some are universal in nature, while others are used to measure specific social and cultural change [14].

The Civil Society Development Index is a new international program that provides countries with the opportunity to continually compare civil society with international standards that will guide its development. Ultimately, this index also serves as a tool for formulating and evaluating development goals and programs and strengthening civil society.

Another indicator of the development of civil society is “The NGO Tolerance Index”. This index was developed by Freedom House and reflects the level of development of non-governmental or non-profit organizations in the country under study. The NGO Tolerance Index is a tool for comparative assessment of the level of development of civil society, which includes seven groups: organizational capacity, financial capacity, law enforcement activities, ability to represent public interests, service delivery, infrastructure and public image. They are measured on a scale of 1 to 7 (1 - good value, 7 - bad value). A score of 1 to 3 indicates that the NGO is resilient, 4 is an average, and 5 to 7 indicates that there are barriers to the development and resilience of the NGO [9].

In recent decades, theoretical views have been developing on the criteria (indicators) of the maturity of civil society and the level of its influence on human development). Scientists define the following indicators of social participation as

one of the criteria for the maturity of civil society and its ability to influence human development:

total number of NGOs;

number of active NGOs;

population involved in NGO activities;

activities and projects implemented with the participation of NGOs;

the extent to which individual NGOs and the media are recognized by the public;

the level of implementation of government decisions made on the basis of public participation;

the amount of funding from NGOs based on funds from various sources;

volume of services provided with the participation of NGOs;

the contribution of NGOs to GDP;

the contribution of NGOs to the success of national programs.

However, in our opinion, the following should be added to the list of these indicators:

development of special indicators for countries experiencing a period of transition (transformation), moving towards building civil society;

indicators of the extent to which NGOs represent the various interests of the individual, the extent to which they are expressed in government decisions;

an indicator of how many proposals and recommendations of NGOs based on the interests of social strata are reflected in national legislation;

an indicator of the extent to which NGOs participate in the activities of public authorities;

an indicator of the level of ability of NGOs to operate independently (de facto) from public authorities in public life;

In general, in our opinion, this creates conditions for the development of the following factors of human self-development in countries that have entered the period of independence and are forming a civil society:

man increases the experience of expressing and defending his interests;

The protection of human interests by NGOs becomes their main goal, they mediate between the state and citizens;

NGOs are directly involved in law-making processes capable of guaranteeing human development;

decentralization of public administration with the growing role of civil society institutions in the management of society and the state;

as a result of participation in the activities of civil society institutions, the level of human socialization increases.

Conclusion

Past experience has shown that civil society countries in Europe and North America are going through stages of civil society building, which requires a much more difficult and difficult transition period. In particular, it should be noted that the history of the Central Asian region did not go through the experience of a market economy and capitalist relations, the absence of a single national market economy in each of the countries of the region hinders the rapid development of civil society reform. In addition, insufficient awareness of “civic engagement” or initiatives of non-governmental organizations (NGOs) as a result of the fact that the national mentality, culture, spirituality, and spirit of the nation are not yet ready to accept democratic values, also has a negative impact on the reforms in the transition period.

To accelerate this process, countries in the current period of transformation of civil society must first end the current authoritarian regime and introduce administrative reforms in the executive branch. That is, when the executive branch weakens in relation to society, the system of state and public administration is decentralized, and ultimately conditions are created for the formation of a civil society. Another important factor in this area is the formation of a class of owners. At the same time, raising the political culture of citizens, expanding their participation in social and political processes, ensuring human rights and freedoms,

expanding freedom of speech and press are important guarantees for building a civil society. In general, civil society is a human cell in which the highest values of humanity prevail and human dignity is respected.

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